

**GULISTAN
STATE
UNIVERSITY**

PERSPECTIVES OF PHILOLOGY AND PRACTICAL POSSIBILITIES OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

**PROCEEDINGS
OF THE INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE**

GULISTAN CITY, MAY 10-11, 2023

THE MINISTRY OF HIGHER EDUCATION, SCIENCE AND INNOVATION
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VA CHET TILLAR O'QITISHNING
AMALIY IMKONIYATLARI**

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“O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta’lim tizimini 2030 yilgacha rivojlantirish kontsepsiyasini tasdiqlash to‘g‘risida” O‘zbekiston Respublika Prezidentining 5847-sonli Farmonida ko‘zda tutilgan vazifalardan biri – ilmiy izlanish yutuklarini amaliyotga joriy etish yo‘li bilan fan sohalarini rivojlantirish, ya’ni xalqaro ilmiy hamjamiyatda e’tirof etilishiga xizmat qilishdir. Konferentsiyani o‘tkazish uchun asosi – O‘zbekiston Respublika Prezidentining 19 may 2021 yildagi 5117-sonli “O‘zbekiston Respublikasida xorijiy tillarni o‘rganishni ommalashtirish faoliyatini sifat jihatidan yangi bosqichga olib chiqish chora-tadbirlari to‘g‘risida” qarori. Shu va boshqa tegishli farmonlarda va qarorlarda belgilangan vazifalarini amalga oshirish maqsadida **2023 yil 10-11 mayda Guliston davlat universiteti “Ingliz tili va adabiyoti” kafedrasidan “Filologiya istiqbollari va chet tillar o‘qitishning amaliy imkoniyatlari”** mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferentsiyasi o‘tkazilgan. Konferentsiya zamonaviy filologiya fanining eng dolzarb ilmiy mavzularini va uslubiy ishlanmalarini aks ettirishga qaratilgan.

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To‘plamga kiritilgan ma’ruza tezislarning mazmuni, undagi ma’lumotlar va me’yoriy hujjatlarning to‘g‘riligi hamda fikr-mulohazalar, keltirilgan takliflarga mualliflarning o‘zlari mas’uldirlar.

Абайнинг ижодий мероси 180 га яқин шеърлари, 3 та поэмаси, 60 дан ортик таржималари ва унчалик катта бўлмаган прозаси ҳамда бир неча тарихий мавзудаги мақолаларидан иборат.

*Мен ўланни ёзмайман эрмак учун,
Ўтган-кетган гапларни термак учун.
Мен ўланни ёзаман тушунганга,
Авлодимга бир сабоқ бермоқ учун,*

деган Абай ўз шеърларида муҳаббатсиз, дўстликсиз ҳаёт бўлиши мумкин эмас, унингсиз жамият учун фойдали ижод қилиб бўлмайди, деб халқини илм олишга, ҳунар эгаллашга, ҳалол меҳнат қилишга чақиради.

Ўз даврининг маърифатпарвари сифатида Абай қозоқ халқининг кўп асрлик меросини янада бойитди. Унинг асарлари маънавий, ахлоқий, ҳажвий маъно ва мазмунда бўлиб, уларни ўрганиш айниқса ёшлар тарбияси учун муҳим аҳамият касб этади. Қозоғистон Президенти Қосим-Жомарт Тоқаев Абайни миллатнинг маънавий ислохотчиси деб айтган [Тоқаев, 2020].

Буюк шоир ва файласуф, маърифатпарвар Абай хотирасига бағишлаб, Алмати, Тошкент, Истанбул, Техрон, Москва ва бошқа шаҳарларда ҳайкаллар ўрнатилган. Унинг номи билан кўчалар аталган. Абайнинг номи ҳамиша барҳаётдир.

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DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES AND LITERARY HYPERTEXT

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Abstract. The article highlights the issue of the influence of digital technologies on the formation and content of modern literary text (hypertext). For this purpose, an analysis of the works of some authors is given in the context of the evolution of hypertext as an art form. Similar and individual characteristics are revealed between the selected books and examples of earlier works of art that have reached the level of hypertext. The influence of digital technologies on this art form is noted, expressed primarily in two opposing trends - imitation of the effects of electronic

text, on the one hand, and emphasizing the materiality of the book and the impossibility of replacing it with a computer, on the other.

Key words: digital technologies, fiction, hypertext, evolution, electronic literature.

“Literature must adapt to the new electronic era,” Milorad Pavić emphasized, offering readers a dictionary novel, a crossword novel, a tarot divination manual novel, or an astrological reference novel [1]. It was in relation to his *Khazar Dictionary* [2], which reviewers dubbed as “the first book of the 21st century”, that the initially purely computer term hypertext was first used. M. Pavić is a discoverer of hypertext in literature, while many of the features attributed to this new art form are also found in the books of other writers, in particular, Julio Cortazar [3], Italo Calvino [4], etc., written much earlier than the *Khazar Dictionary*, and sometimes even before the appearance of the term “hypertext” itself. However, it is in the *Khazar Dictionary* that these features are most fully manifested, which allowed Yasmina Mikhailovich to suggest that it would be much more convenient to read this book behind a computer monitor [5]. The form of literary hypertext, indeed, is the best fit for the new computer era, meeting all the features of “electronic” reading. Following the *Khazar Dictionary*, a whole series of electronic literary hypertexts appeared. It is also the first computer-readable novel, “Afternoon, a Story” by Michael Joyce [6], followed by “Patchwork Girl” by Shelley Jackson [7], “Uncle Buddy's Phantom Funhouse” by John McDaid [8], “Its name was Penelope” by Judy Mallow [9], etc. As a result, there was an opinion that only electronic novels created for reading at a computer and using its specific capabilities belong to literary hypertexts. “There can be no printed equivalent for this literature” [10], emphasized Michael Joyce, reinforcing the impression that the literary hypertext in the book, and not in the electronic version, if it appeared earlier in the same *Khazar Dictionary*, it was only because in 1984 it was not possible to create novels for the computer. “We are at the end of the print age; the time for books is over. A book is an incomprehensible pleasure, like opera or cigars” [10], explains M. Joyce. The end of the printed era in the same 1991 was also proclaimed by another supporter of electronic literature, Jay Bolter [11]. Robert Coover publishes an article with the characteristic title “The End of Books”, where he emphasizes that “real freedom from the tyranny of the line has become possible only now, with the advent of hypertext, written and read by a computer...” [12]. However, in 2000 statements about the “death” of the book, and with it the traditional “book” literature, which should be replaced by electronic literature, have almost completely disappeared. Moreover, Michael Joyce, who once called the book “incomprehensible pleasure”, himself releases several novels not on his usual CD, but in the form of a traditional book: “Disappearance”; “Going the Distance”; “Twentieth Century Man” [13].

This paper will consider the further development of literary hypertext precisely as a book, and not an electronic form. In this regard, we will analyze the hypertext novels of two American authors: “House of Leaves” by Mark Z. Danielewski [14] and “Tree of Codes” by Jonathan S. Foer [15]. Their form is quite traditional: they were published in the form of a paper book. Since literary hypertext and electronic literature are relatively new phenomena, there are not so many monographs devoted to their study today. Among the most significant of them, it is worth noting the works of the “pioneers” of electronic literature “Hypertext: The Convergence of Contemporary Critical Theory and Technology” by George P. Landow [16] and “Writing Space” by Jay D. Bolter [11]. Both authors under the concept of “hypertext” meant exclusively electronic literature, and hyperlinks were called its main distinguishing feature. Both J. P. Landow and J. D. Bolter emphasized that it was hyperlinks that made it possible to radically change the principle of reading

a work of art, giving the reader the opportunity to choose which way to move through the text. When comparing N.K. Hales' monographs, among which "Writing Machines" [17] and "Electronic Literature: new horizons for the literary" [18] are especially worth noting, with the studies of J. D. Bolter and J. P. Landow, it becomes obvious how electronic literature and literary hypertext have evolved in just over 15 years. If in the early 1990s *Afternoon, a Story* by Michael Joyce was considered a model of electronic literature, in 2008 N.K. Hales calls this novel too "printcentric" [18], as it lacks the main features of modern electronic literature - sound files, graphics, an extensive color palette, external links, etc. N.K. Hales also draws attention to modern book literature and proves that the latter, although not intended for reading at a computer, is still strongly influenced by new technologies and is inherently electronic. Just like the electronic text of N.K. Hales considers, in particular, the book by M.Z. Danilewski "House of Leaves". The researcher notes that the use of computer text editors, image processing programs, etc. significantly influenced this book, bringing it closer in its qualities to an electronic text.

The novelty of this article lies in the analysis of the works of M.Z. Danilewski and J.S. Foer in the context of the evolution of literary hypertext. If N.K. Hales, as well as other researchers, among whom M. Hansen [19] and J. Pressman [20] can be distinguished, consider "House of Leaves" only from the point of view of modern technologies, we will try to compare the above-mentioned books, as well as with electronic novels, and with printed hypertexts. This will make it possible to clarify which features in "House of Leaves" and "Tree of Codes" really refer exclusively to the influence of new technologies, and which ones can be seen, for example, in M. Pavić's *Khazar Dictionary*, written before the advent of the Internet era.

The working hypothesis of the study is the statement that the hypertexts of M.Z. Danilewski and J.S. Foer continue the tradition of twentieth-century experimental literature. and, above all, the novels of M. Pavić. New technologies have allowed writers to develop in their works many features that were only outlined in literary hypertexts before the digital era and were clearly manifested in electronic literature. But first, let's dwell on what a literary hypertext is. One of the first definitions of this concept was given by George P. Landow: "This is a text consisting of verbal blocks (or images) that are connected by electronic links and create numerous routes, networks or paths in an open, fundamentally incomplete text..." [16]. This definition seems incomplete to us, because it implies that only electronic novels can be hypertexts. It does not take into account the possibility of the existence of hypertext in the book. In this article, we will use the hypertext formulation given by N.E. Mikeladze: "Hypertext is a text with many connections, "inputs" and "outputs". This text is fluid, multi-level, mobile. It is based on the principle of hyperlinks connecting its constituent fragments... And like an architectural structure, such a text is based and perceived already according to the logic, not of time, but of space" [21]. To the main features of the literary hypertext N.E. Mikeladze attributes: fragmentation, spatial form of narration, lack of fixed plots, climaxes and denouements, semantic, compositional and structural looseness of parts, lack of causal relationships, the possibility of multiple interpretations and interactivity [22].

All these features are characteristic of Mark Z. Danilewski's book "House of Leaves", the plot of which is based on the fact that an unremarkable tattoo parlor employee Johnny Truant finds manuscripts of his recently deceased neighbor – old man Zampano. He discovers that this is serious scientific research on the famous film "The Navidson Record" - "serious" if you do not consider that such a film existed only in Zampano's imagination. As a result, the reader is faced with a 700-page book, which consists of several texts of various types. A retelling of the plot of the documentary "The Navidson Record", which is more reminiscent of a horror film in genre. The

film was shot by famous photojournalist Will Navidson, who moved with his wife and two children to a new house, in which an endless labyrinth is hidden behind one of the doors. Zampano's monograph, devoted to the analysis of the film "The Navidson Record", is in a scientific style. Zampano provides his work with references and quotations from other researchers. We learn that there are many schools of thought that have been arguing violently about the film. Explaining the plot twists and turns and the psychology of the characters, the researchers turn to Freud, Heidegger, Borges, etc. for help. The names of real people and references to real-life books are mixed with fictitious sources. The story of Johnny Truant, who found the manuscripts, we learn from the footnotes with which he supplied Zampano's text. From the world of the thriller and the world of scientific research, we find ourselves in the third world - the world of a person who spends his life going to clubs, drinking, dating, etc. Letters from the mother of Johnny Truant from the insane asylum and, accordingly, the fourth reality - the world of a woman going crazy. Nevertheless, Danilewski's novel becomes a bestseller. Probably, the reason for this should be sought not only in the content, but also in the form of the book, which, according to the writer, is most appropriate for the modern era: "faced with magazines, newspapers, radio, television and, of course, the Internet, people ... got used to the simultaneous processing huge layers of information" [23]. Many features of M. Danilevsky's book echo the novels of M. Pavić, and some of the tricks of playing with the reader seem to be taken directly from the books of the Serbian writer. "In this place lies a reader who will never open this book. Here he sleeps forever" [2] – we read at the very beginning of the *Khazar Dictionary*; "It's not for you" [24], - we meet in the same place in "House of Leaves". M. Danilewski, like M. Pavić, focuses on the figure of an active reader-co-author who takes part in the creation of the book. It is no coincidence that he makes the reader, Johnny Truant, one of the main characters of "House of Leaves". Truant demonstrates by his example how to read this book (which is reminiscent of Pavić's preliminary reading instructions).

"Tree of Codes" by Jonathan Safran Foer and "House of Leaves" by Mark Danilewski do not simply adopt the features of the literary hypertext of Milorad Pavić. Although Pavić explained the features of his works by the "electronic era", the *Khazar Dictionary* was nevertheless written in 1984, that is, before its actual onset. The novels of M. Danilewski and J. S. Foer were created much later, when the computer and the Internet were already firmly established in life. The influence of new technologies in them is more obvious. Many of the tendencies that were only outlined by M. Pavić are manifested more clearly here, reminiscent of not book, but electronic hypertexts by Michael Joyce and other writers. Comparing the books of M. Danilewski and J. S. Foer with the hypertexts of M. Pavić, it is necessary to note the increased visualization. It manifests itself primarily in the wider use of illustrations. So in "House of Leaves" the illustrations become part of the book's playful intent. Their task is to emphasize the reality of Nevidson's film and Zampano's text. The reader is offered a model of the Nevidson house with the name of its author, as well as the date and place of creation. We also see a canvas by an artist inspired by the film (again, with the name of the artist and information about which exhibitions it was presented at). We are given a screenshot of one of the episodes of the film, an excerpt from a comic strip dedicated to it, as well as several photos of the house itself from different angles. Johnny Truant also demonstrates photographs depicting Zampano's manuscripts: something is printed, something is written by hand, something is burned out, crossed out, as described in the text of the book. As a result, the reader gets a feeling of the absolute reality of what is written. So many documents testify to it, provided also with references to primary sources, that it is impossible to doubt. True, until you start looking for at least one of the indicated names on the Internet. Even a cursory glance at the

illustrations in "House of Leaves" is striking how thoughtful they are. The author obviously devoted a lot of time to them. He expects the same from the reader, who must carefully examine the material offered to him and find in it something that does not lie on the surface.

The active use of illustrations is typical for M. Danielewsky, and other of his works speak of this. In the book "The Fifty Year Sword" [25], the number of illustrations only increases. Moreover, they literally begin to visualize the text. For example, when the Storyteller (one of the main characters in the book) brings five orphans a mysterious box with five latches, on the next page we see a black background with five latches. Turning the page, we read that the first boy moved the first latch, on the next page we see the same drawing, only now one latch is raised. We turn over – the second child moves the valve, and now two valves remain in the illustration at the top, etc. And, finally, the climax - all the valves are raised, the storyteller opens the lid. We have to turn the page again. But on the next spread, there is no text - we have two black pages in front of us. We turn the page again and read that the children were also indignant because the box was empty. There are no illustrations in "Tree of Codes" - this is not the main game principle of this book. However, literary critics have repeatedly noted its unusual design, which allows us to speak of "Tree of Codes" not just as a literary work, but as a "work of art" in a broader sense of the word [26].

J.S. Foer, after the book was published, said that it was important for him to create such a book that, upon opening it for the first time, the reader would be surprised and think: "This is not at all what I expected!" [26]. And, indeed, the novel, consisting of almost 140 cut pages, creates just such an effect on the reader, as evidenced by the promotional video posted even before its release on the publisher's website. The focus of his attention is not the book itself, but the unusual reaction of readers who were invited to open it and read [26]. The increase in visualization is expressed in the active use of font and color capabilities. M. Danielewsky's text is not necessarily black letters on a white background, the author often uses color. So the word "house" is always highlighted in blue, and all the passages dedicated to the Minotaur are in red and also crossed out, as if the author of the manuscript wanted to delete them, but did not have time to do so. As a result, along with the imitation of electronic links, it also creates the feeling that this is not text printed on a computer, but handwritten. Moreover, the very form of the text often serves as a means of visualizing its content. Instead of the traditional text, which is read from right to left from top to bottom, we see in "House of Leaves" more sophisticated constructions, which manifest the state of mind of the numerous "authors" of the book. For example, in letters to Johnny Truant's mother, letters can creep on letters, lines on lines, sometimes making the text completely unreadable, which conveys the state of mind of a woman in a psychiatric hospital.

With the help of playing with the form, M. Danielewsky not only emphasizes the psychological state of the characters. In "House of Leaves" often the form of the text directly depends on its content. The pace of reading a book also directly depends on the pace of the events taking place in it. Zampano's "scientific" reasoning is written in long sentences, with many references. Just as nothing happens at this moment in the text, the book begins to be read with difficulty. But as soon as we "get" into the chapter where Navidson races on a bicycle through the endless maze of his house, the reader "rushes" according to the text. Only a few words are written on each page, the reader quickly flips through page after page.

A large number of illustrations, unusual design, use of color, different fonts, imitation of cinematic effects, as well as constant references to other media - newspapers, books, the Internet - allow us to talk about the multimodality of literary hypertext. Initially, the term "multimodality",

meaning the interweaving of visual material (and often audio and video files) into the text, was applicable only to electronic literature and was considered its hallmark. So, an electronic text cannot be evaluated without taking into account the visual (and/or sound) design, which is as much a part of the work as the text itself. But the same can be said about hypertexts written by some modern writers.

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WIDESPREAD USAGE OF METAPHORS IN LITERARY TEXTS

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